

THE EFFECT OF INVESTMENT, REGIONAL ORIGINAL REVENUE (PAD), GENERAL ALLOCATION FUND (DAU), AND REGIONAL EXPENDITURE ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN REGENCIES AND MUNICIPALITIES OF WEST PAPUA PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

Economic growth is an important indicator of regional development influenced by economic and fiscal factors, including investment, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), General Allocation Fund (DAU), and regional expenditure. This study aims to analyze the effect of investment, PAD, DAU, and regional expenditure on the economic growth of regencies/cities in West Papua Province during 2019–2022, both simultaneously and partially. The study employed a quantitative approach using secondary data obtained from Statistics Indonesia, the Directorate General of Fiscal Balance, and the Ministry of Investment and Downstream Industry/BKPM. Data were analyzed using multiple linear regression with SPSS version 22 through descriptive statistical tests, classical assumption tests, F-test, t-test, and coefficient of determination. The results show that all variables simultaneously have a significant effect on economic growth. Partially, investment has no significant effect, while PAD and regional expenditure have a positive significant effect, and DAU has a negative significant effect. Regional expenditure is the most dominant variable, with a coefficient of determination of 87%.

Keywords: Investment, Regional Original Revenue, General Allocation Fund, Regional Expenditure, Economic Growth.

INTRODUCTION

Economic development is a multidimensional process aimed at improving public welfare through increased income, employment opportunities, and equitable development. The success of economic development is generally measured by economic growth, which is reflected in the increase of Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). Adam Smith's classical economic growth theory explains that economic growth is influenced by population development, capital accumulation, and the division of labor, all of which enhance labor productivity (Jhingan, 2018). Meanwhile, Solow's neoclassical growth theory emphasizes the importance of technological advancement and the quality of human resources in promoting economic growth.

Investment is one of the key determinants of economic growth because it enhances production capacity and creates employment opportunities. Sukirno (2000) explains that investment refers to capital expenditures intended to increase the production of goods and services. The Harrod–Domar theory and Schumpeter's innovation theory (1934) further emphasize that investment and innovation play significant roles in fostering sustainable regional economic development.

In the era of fiscal decentralization, the ability of local governments to manage regional finances also plays a crucial role in determining economic growth. According to Oates' Fiscal Federalism Theory (1972), local governments possess a better understanding of their regional needs, making fiscal management more effective. Regional Original Revenue (Pendapatan Asli Daerah/PAD) reflects the degree of regional fiscal independence and positively influences economic growth (Kuncoro, 2012). In addition, the General Allocation Fund (Dana Alokasi Umum/DAU) and regional expenditure play important roles in supporting development, particularly when allocated to productive sectors (Wibowo & Kaluge, 2019). West Papua Province continues to face development challenges due to limited infrastructure, geographical constraints, and disparities in economic growth among regencies and municipalities. Table 1 presents the economic growth rates of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province from 2019 to 2022.

Table 1. Economic Growth Rates of Regencies/Municipalities in West Papua Province, 2019–2022

Regency/Municipality	2019	2020	2021	2022
Fakfak	5.29	-2.95	0.97	1.85
Kaimana	3.71	-2.83	-2.10	1.03
Teluk Wondama	4.18	-3.22	1.09	3.19
Teluk Bintuni	3.41	1.06	-2.30	2.01
Manokwari	3.60	-6.27	3.69	2.05
South Sorong	5.69	-3.67	3.47	5.71
Raja Ampat	4.16	-2.28	11.79	11.89
Arfak Mountains	6.91	6.07	4.55	13.39
West Papua	4.76	-1.99	1.97	4.06

Source: Statistics Indonesia (BPS) of West Papua Province

Based on Table 1, the economic growth of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province exhibited considerable fluctuations. In 2020, most regions experienced economic contraction due to the COVID-19 pandemic. Manokwari Regency recorded negative growth of -6.27 percent, while South Sorong and Teluk Wondama also experienced economic slowdowns. During the 2021–2022 period, economic recovery occurred; however, the pace of recovery varied across regions. Raja Ampat Regency achieved growth of 11.89 percent, whereas several other regions continued to record relatively low growth rates. This condition indicates disparities in economic activities among regions in West Papua. One of the strategic investments in West Papua is the LNG Tangguh Train 3 Project in Teluk Bintuni Regency, with an investment value of approximately US\$4.83 billion.

Table 2. Regional Revenue, PAD, and DAU in West Papua Province

Type of Revenue	2019	2020	2021	2022
PAD (Billion IDR)	483.73	485.37	486.19	485.37
DAU (Billion IDR)	1,456.52	1,299.87	1,350.98	1,307.71

Source: Statistics Indonesia (BPS) of West Papua Province

The data indicate that the contribution of PAD remains relatively small compared to DAU. This condition suggests that the fiscal capacity of local governments to independently finance development remains limited, resulting in substantial dependence on central government transfers. According to Mardiasmo (2018), high fiscal dependence may reduce development effectiveness if it is not accompanied by productive expenditure management and the optimization of PAD.

In addition to regional revenue, regional expenditure management is also an important factor in promoting economic growth. The expenditure structure of the West Papua Provincial Government remains dominated by operational expenditure rather than capital expenditure.

Table 3. Expenditure Structure of the West Papua Provincial Government

Type of Expenditure	2019	2020	2021	2022
Operational Expenditure	5.44	6.63	3.27	3.41
Capital Expenditure	1.76	1.54	2.43	2.20
Transfer Expenditure	3.86	4.40	2.05	1.89

Source: Statistics Indonesia (BPS) of West Papua Province

The dominance of operational expenditure indicates that a large proportion of the regional budget is still allocated to routine governmental activities. Meanwhile, capital expenditure, which is directly associated with infrastructure development and the enhancement of regional economic capacity, remains relatively limited and fluctuating. According to Musgrave (1959), development expenditure plays a strategic role in generating sustainable economic growth.

Previous studies have produced mixed findings regarding the effects of investment, PAD, DAU, and regional expenditure on economic growth. Kuncoro (2012) found that PAD positively affects regional economic growth. Wibowo and Kaluge (2019) reported that DAU has a positive impact when allocated to productive expenditures. Mardiasmo (2018) emphasized that the quality of regional expenditure is a key determinant of the success of regional fiscal policies. However, most previous studies were conducted in provinces on Java and Sumatra, which possess economic and fiscal characteristics different from those of West Papua.

Given these conditions, studies examining the relationships among these variables in special autonomous regions and areas with high fiscal dependence remain relatively limited. Furthermore, West Papua possesses unique geographical characteristics, economic structures, and fiscal capacities compared to other regions in Indonesia, thereby requiring more specific empirical investigation. The findings of this study are expected to provide empirical contributions and policy recommendations for local governments in improving the effectiveness of regional financial management and promoting sustainable economic growth.

METHOD

This study employed a quantitative approach using an explanatory research design to analyze the effects of investment, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), General Allocation Fund (DAU), and regional expenditure on economic growth in the regencies and municipalities of West Papua Province. The study covered all regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province during the 2019–2022 period and utilized secondary panel data, which combine cross-sectional data (regencies/municipalities) and time-series data (observation periods).

The population of this study consisted of all eight regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province, namely Fakfak, Kaimana, Teluk Wondama, Teluk Bintuni, Manokwari, South Sorong, Raja Ampat, and Arfak Mountains. A saturated sampling (census) technique was employed, whereby the entire population was included as the research sample. With a four-year observation period (2019–2022), a total of 32 observation units were obtained.

The data used in this study were secondary data obtained from official publications of Statistics Indonesia (BPS) of West Papua Province, the Directorate General of Fiscal Balance (DJPK) of the Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia, and the Ministry of Investment/Indonesia Investment Coordinating Board (BKPM). The dependent variable was economic growth, proxied by the growth rate of Gross Regional Domestic Product (GRDP). The independent variables consisted of investment (X1), Regional Original Revenue (PAD) (X2), General Allocation Fund (DAU) (X3), and regional expenditure (X4).

Multiple linear regression analysis was employed to analyze the data. Prior to hypothesis testing, the data were subjected to classical assumption tests, including normality, multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and autocorrelation tests. Hypothesis testing was subsequently conducted using the simultaneous significance test (F-test), partial significance test (t-test), and coefficient of determination (R^2) analysis to assess the explanatory power of the independent variables on variations in economic growth. Data processing was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 22.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistical Analysis Results

Descriptive statistical analysis was conducted to provide a general overview of the characteristics of the research data, which include investment, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), General Allocation Fund (DAU), regional expenditure, and economic growth of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province. The results of the descriptive statistical analysis are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistical Analysis Results

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
LN Economic Growth (Y)	52	4.96	10.15	7.4880	1.54238
LN_INV (X1)	43	-4.61	6.98	3.6119	3.07613
LN_PAD (X2)	52	1.18	4.69	3.4147	0.93863

Variable	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
LN_DAU (X3)	52	5.76	6.55	6.1707	0.20670
LN_RE (X4)	52	6.48	8.01	7.0503	0.30329

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on Table 4, the economic growth variable has a mean value of 7.4880 with a standard deviation of 1.54238. The investment variable has a mean value of 3.6119 and a standard deviation of 3.07613, indicating a relatively high level of data dispersion. The PAD variable has a mean value of 3.4147 with a standard deviation of 0.93863. Meanwhile, the DAU and regional expenditure variables have average values of 6.1707 and 7.0503, respectively. These results indicate that the research data exhibit sufficient variation to be used in multiple linear regression analysis.

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Multiple linear regression analysis was employed to examine the effects of investment, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), General Allocation Fund (DAU), and regional expenditure on the economic growth of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province.

Table 5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variable	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	-3.320	3.752	-	-0.885	0.382
LN_INV (X1)	0.028	0.030	0.062	0.939	0.354
LN_PAD (X2)	1.037	0.138	0.683	7.496	0.000
LN_DAU (X3)	-0.815	0.533	-0.116	-1.530	0.134
LN_RE (X4)	1.751	0.359	0.378	4.876	0.000

$R^2 = 0.870$

F-statistic = 63.673

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on the regression results presented in Table 5, the coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.870, indicating that investment, PAD, DAU, and regional expenditure collectively explain 87% of the variation in economic growth, while the remaining 13% is explained by other variables not included in this study. PAD and regional expenditure have positive and statistically significant effects on economic growth. In contrast, investment and DAU do not exhibit significant effects. These findings suggest that regional fiscal capacity and government expenditure management play important roles in enhancing regional economic growth.

Classical Assumption Test Results

a. Normality Test

Table 6. Kolmogorov–Smirnov Normality Test Results

Description	Value
N	43
Test Statistic	0.081
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on Table 6, the Asymp. Sig. value is 0.200, which is greater than the significance level of 0.05. This result indicates that the residual data are normally distributed. Therefore, the regression model satisfies the normality assumption and is appropriate for further hypothesis testing.

b. Multicollinearity Test

Table 7. Multicollinearity Test Results

Variable	Tolerance	VIF
LN_INV (X1)	0.792	1.263
LN_PAD (X2)	0.412	2.427
LN_DAU (X3)	0.590	1.695
LN_RE (X4)	0.569	1.759

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on the multicollinearity test results presented in Table 7, all independent variables have tolerance values greater than 0.10 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values below 10. These results indicate that the regression model does not suffer from multicollinearity problems. Therefore, the relationships among the independent variables do not interfere with the accuracy of the regression model used in this study.

c. Autocorrelation Test

Table 8. Durbin–Watson Autocorrelation Test Results

Model	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Durbin–Watson
1	0.870	0.857	1.458

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on the autocorrelation test results shown in Table 8, the Durbin–Watson statistic is 1.458. This value falls within the inconclusive region, lying between the lower and upper critical values of the Durbin–Watson test. Nevertheless, the regression model can still be utilized for analysis because it does not indicate strong symptoms of autocorrelation.

d. Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 9. Glejser Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Variable	Sig.
LN_INV (X1)	0.242

Variable	Sig.
LN_PAD (X ₂)	0.411
LN_DAU (X ₃)	0.500
LN_RE (X ₄)	0.359

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on the heteroscedasticity test results presented in Table 9, all independent variables have significance values greater than 0.05. These findings indicate that the regression model does not exhibit heteroscedasticity problems. Therefore, the residual variance is constant, and the model satisfies the homoscedasticity assumption.

Hypothesis Testing Results

a. Simultaneous Test (F-Test)

Table 10. Simultaneous Test (F-Test) Results

F-statistic	Sig.
41.119	0.000

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on the simultaneous test results presented in Table 10, the F-statistic value is 41.119 with a significance level of 0.000. Since the significance value is less than 0.05, it can be concluded that investment, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), General Allocation Fund (DAU), and regional expenditure simultaneously have a significant effect on the economic growth of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province.

b. Partial Test (t-Test)

Table 11. Partial Test (t-Test) Results

Variable	t-value	Sig.	Interpretation
LN_INV (X ₁)	-1.158	0.254	Not Significant
LN_PAD (X ₂)	2.657	0.011	Significant
LN_DAU (X ₃)	-3.888	0.000	Significant
LN_RE (X ₄)	9.137	0.000	Significant

Source: Processed Secondary Data, 2026.

Based on the partial test results shown in Table 11, the investment variable does not significantly affect economic growth, as indicated by a significance value of 0.254, which exceeds 0.05. Meanwhile, PAD and regional expenditure have positive and significant effects on economic growth. In contrast, DAU has a negative and significant effect on the economic growth of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province.

The Effect of Investment on Economic Growth in Regencies and Municipalities of West Papua Province

Based on the partial test results, the investment variable has a significance value of 0.254, which is greater than 0.05. Therefore, investment does not have a significant effect

on the economic growth of regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province. The regression coefficient of investment indicates a negative direction, suggesting that increases in investment have not yet generated a substantial impact on regional economic growth during the study period. These findings imply that investment activities in West Papua have not been able to optimally stimulate economic activities.

Theoretically, investment is one of the key determinants of economic growth because it increases production capacity, creates employment opportunities, and expands economic activities. However, investment can only generate optimal outcomes when supported by adequate infrastructure, a conducive business environment, and high-quality human resources. In the context of this study, investment inflows into West Papua are presumed to remain relatively exclusive and not yet fully integrated with local community economic activities.

Therefore, local governments should improve investment quality through more equitable infrastructure development, simplification of licensing procedures, and enhancement of local workforce capabilities so that incoming investments can generate greater multiplier effects on the regional economy. Furthermore, investments should be encouraged in productive sectors directly linked to local communities, such as agriculture, fisheries, micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), and processing industries.

The Effect of Regional Original Revenue (PAD) on Economic Growth in Regencies and Municipalities of West Papua Province

The results indicate that Regional Original Revenue (PAD) has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in the regencies and municipalities of West Papua Province. This finding is evidenced by a significance value of 0.011, which is lower than 0.05, and a positive regression coefficient. These results suggest that higher PAD is associated with higher levels of regional economic growth.

PAD reflects the ability of local governments to generate revenue from local economic potential through local taxes, service charges, management of regional assets, and other legitimate sources of revenue. Regions with higher PAD generally possess stronger fiscal capacity to finance infrastructure development, public services, education, healthcare, and other economic development programs. Such conditions directly stimulate economic activities and promote regional economic growth.

In the context of West Papua, increasing PAD is particularly important given the region's continuing need for infrastructure development and public service expansion. Therefore, local governments should continue to optimize PAD sources by improving the effectiveness of local tax collection, developing local economic potential, and managing regional assets more productively. Optimizing PAD is expected to enhance regional fiscal independence and support more sustainable economic development.

The Effect of the General Allocation Fund (DAU) on Economic Growth in Regencies and Municipalities of West Papua Province

Based on the partial test results, the General Allocation Fund (DAU) variable has a negative and significant effect on economic growth in the regencies and municipalities of

West Papua Province. This is indicated by a significance value of 0.000, which is lower than 0.05, along with a negative regression coefficient. These findings suggest that increases in DAU have not been able to optimally stimulate regional economic growth.

The negative effect of DAU indicates that larger fiscal transfers from the central government are not necessarily accompanied by increased regional economic productivity. This condition may occur when DAU allocations are primarily directed toward routine government expenditures, such as personnel expenses and administrative costs, rather than productive expenditures capable of stimulating economic activities.

In the context of West Papua, local governments need to improve the effectiveness of DAU utilization by allocating funds to programs that directly enhance community economic productivity. In addition, strengthening planning and budget monitoring capacities is necessary to ensure that transfer funds generate greater economic benefits for society.

The Effect of Regional Expenditure on Economic Growth in Regencies and Municipalities of West Papua Province

The findings indicate that regional expenditure has a positive and significant effect on economic growth in the regencies and municipalities of West Papua Province. Regional expenditure is also identified as the most dominant variable affecting economic growth, with a standardized beta coefficient of 0.852. This result demonstrates that increases in regional expenditure can stimulate economic activities and promote regional economic growth.

In the context of West Papua, regional expenditure plays a crucial role because the region still requires extensive infrastructure development and basic public services. The high dependence of local communities on government-led development initiatives makes regional expenditure management a key driver of economic growth.

Therefore, local governments should ensure that regional expenditure is allocated effectively, efficiently, and appropriately, particularly toward sectors that directly enhance community productivity. Strengthening investments in infrastructure, education, healthcare, MSMEs, and leading regional economic sectors is expected to generate greater multiplier effects and support sustainable economic growth across regencies and municipalities in West Papua Province.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of this study examining the effects of investment, Regional Original Revenue (PAD), General Allocation Fund (DAU), and regional expenditure on economic growth in the regencies and municipalities of West Papua Province, it can be concluded that investment does not have a significant effect on regional economic growth. Meanwhile, PAD and regional expenditure have positive and significant effects on economic growth, whereas DAU has a negative and significant effect. The findings also reveal that regional expenditure is the most dominant variable influencing economic growth in the regencies and municipalities of West Papua Province. These results indicate

that the effectiveness of regional fiscal management, particularly through the optimization of PAD and regional expenditure, plays a critical role in promoting regional economic growth.

Local governments are expected to enhance the effectiveness of regional financial management by optimizing PAD, improving investment quality, and allocating DAU and regional expenditure toward productive sectors that can stimulate economic growth. Furthermore, governments should strengthen budget planning and monitoring mechanisms to ensure that regional development programs are implemented effectively and achieve their intended objectives.

Future researchers are encouraged to incorporate additional variables that may influence economic growth, extend the observation period and geographical coverage, and employ more diverse analytical methods to generate more comprehensive findings.

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